

QUIZ**LAST NAME: BLACKMER****FIRST NAME: GENEVA****PROGRAM CODE : DIRD****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA/CLEENEWERCK****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: MSOffice ProPlus

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

- 1. The Turabian rule of style recommends that primary sources be used to demonstrate evidence. What is an example of a primary source?**
 - Books, articles and other materials which analyze data from first-hand accounts.*
 - First-hand account data in the form of words, images, sounds, observations and experiments.¹*
 - Encyclopedias, dictionaries and other sources which provide introductory overviews.*
 - Websites such as Wikipedia which allow all users to freely edit content.*
- 2. At Euclid University, students are required to submit academic papers in English, adhering to standards of writing in either the United States or the United Kingdom. In order to demonstrate consistency, please**

¹ Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses and Dissertations*. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2013, 24-25.

select which of the following applies to rules of spelling, grammar and punctuation in the United States.

- The proper spelling is “colour,” not “color.”*
- Punctuation should be placed outside of quotation marks. (“She went to the store”.)*
- Punctuation should be placed inside quotation marks. (“She went to the store.”)²*
- The proper spelling is “organisation” not “organization.”*

3. According to Turabian, what is required of an author when they are presenting an argument?

- The author must establish what they are claiming, what their reasons are, and what evidence supports these reasons.³*
- The author does not need to consider and respond to imagined questions on behalf of the reader.*
- The author must only test their claim, not support it.*
- The author does not need to consider alternative points of view.*

4. There are two citation styles relevant to the Turabian rule of style: The Notes-Bibliography style and the Author-Date style. What is the primary difference between the two?

- The Author-Date style uses footnotes and the Notes-Bibliography styles uses parenthetical citations.*

² EUCLID. 2015. *ACA-401 Coursepack*. Washington DC: Euclid University. <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/> (accessed August 12, 2019), 54-59.

³ Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses and Dissertations*, 42.

- The Notes-Bibliography styles does not require a full bibliography at the end of the paper.*
 - The Author-Date style does not require a full bibliography at the end of the paper.*
 - The Notes-Bibliography style uses footnotes and the Author-Date styles uses parenthetical citations.⁴*
5. **According to Bloomberg & Volpe, it is important to understand the difference between a topic and a problem. Which of the following properly establishes the difference?**
- Topics define the need for the study.*
 - A topic is a general area of interest, which is progressively narrowed and defined. Research problems are more specific, seeking deeper understanding of a certain aspect of a topic.⁵*
 - A research problem is a general area of interest, which is progressively narrowed and defined. Topics are more specific, seeking deeper understanding of a certain aspect of a topic.*
 - In a research problem, it is not necessary to establish the intellectual value of the study.*
6. **What is the difference between data analysis and data synthesis?**
- Data synthesis involves various approaches, including quasi-statistical, template, editing, and immersion.*
 - Data analysis does not need to be evaluated in terms of consistency.*

⁴ Ibid, 87-88.

⁵ Bloomberg, Linda D. & Volpe, Marie. 2008. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 34-35.

*Data analysis involves a series of individual parts. Data synthesis presents an integrated and holistic picture of the data, providing a context for interpretation.*⁶

Data synthesis involves a series of individual parts. Data analysis presents an integrated and holistic picture of the data, providing a context for interpretation.

7. What is not a component of the dissertation process?

*Writing about your opinion on a topic without providing any evidence to support your claim.*⁷

Adopting a research approach and strategy.

Completing data analysis and synthesis.

Selecting a topic and developing a statement of purpose.

8. When writing a dissertation, authors typically make knowledge claims about what they assume to learn. What are the four schools of thought these claims typically follow?

Classicism, deconstruction, critical theory/advocacy, and post positivism.

*Post positivism, social constructivism, critical theory/advocacy, and pragmatism.*⁸

Aristotelianism, post positivism, social constructivism, and pragmatism.

Empiricism, liberalism, Neoplatonism, and objectivism.

⁶ Ibid, 133-134.

⁷ Ibid, 1-3.

⁸ Ibid, 8-9.

9. **What are the Treaties which founded the European Union?**

- The ECSC Treaty, EEC Treaty, and the Euratom Treaty.***⁹
- The Treaty of Amsterdam, the EEC Treaty, and the Euratom Treaty.*
- The Treaty of Lisbon, the ECSC Treaty, and the EEC Treaty.*
- The Single European Act (SEA), the Treaty of Amsterdam, and the Treaty of Lisbon.*

10. **Which of the following countries are current member states of the European Union?**

- Austria, Germany, Denmark, and the United States.*
- Luxemburg, Malta, Netherlands, and Russia.*
- Austria, Germany, Denmark, and France.***¹⁰
- Russia, Slovenia, Belgium, and Cyprus.*

⁹ The European Commission. 2011. "English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission." Accessed September 7, 2019. <https://euclid.egnyte.com/dl/xitMjHAGfJ/>, 52.

¹⁰ Ibid, 72.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.